

RESEARCH ARTICLE

$\mathfrak{N}_{\mathcal{S}}$ $\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}\mathfrak{Nl}$ and $\mathfrak{N}_{\overline{\mathcal{QS}}}\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}\mathfrak{Nl}$ - Spaces in $\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ -Nano Topological Space

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Abstract

Objectives: The purpose of this study is to propose a new kind of Nano Ideal topological space called $\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ -Nano topological space, explores several novel forms of open and closed sets in the context of $\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ -Nano topological space, and generate $\mathfrak{N}_{\mathcal{S}}$ $\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}\mathfrak{Nl}$ and $\mathfrak{N}_{\overline{\mathcal{QS}}}\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}\mathfrak{Nl}$ -spaces in $\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ -Nano topological space. **Methods:** The $\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ -lower, $\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ -upper and $\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ -boundary regions have been established for any subset of the specified universal set and any binary relation defined on it. The associated $\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ -Nano topological space can be determined by these regions in addition with universal set and the empty set. **Findings:** The relationship between $\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ -Nano open sets and other sets in $\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ -Nano topological spaces are found. Additionally, we figure out the forms of $\mathfrak{N}_{\mathcal{S}}$ $\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}\mathfrak{Nl}$ and $\mathfrak{N}_{\overline{\mathcal{QS}}}\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}\mathfrak{Nl}$ -spaces. **Novelty:** Nano-open sets were used in the formation of normal spaces in Nano topological spaces, whereas in the current research work $\mathfrak{N}\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ and $\mathfrak{N}_{\mathcal{S}}\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ -open sets have been used to generate $\mathfrak{N}_{\mathcal{S}}$ $\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}\mathfrak{Nl}$ and $\mathfrak{N}_{\overline{\mathcal{QS}}}\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}\mathfrak{Nl}$ -spaces. **Keywords:** $\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ -Nano topological space; $\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ -lower, $\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ -upper; $\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ -boundary region, $\mathfrak{N}_{\mathcal{S}}$ $\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}\mathfrak{Nl}$ -space, $\mathfrak{N}_{\overline{\mathcal{QS}}}\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}\mathfrak{Nl}$ -space

1 Introduction

Nano Ideal topological structure has emerged as an essential feature of Nano topological spaces. The Various types of generalized closed sets and open sets in Nano Ideal topological spaces were analyzed⁽¹⁻⁵⁾. The characterizations of different normal spaces in Nano Ideal topological spaces have been studied⁽⁶⁻⁸⁾. The key contribution of the current work is that we provide a novel method to generate Nano Ideal topological space referred to as $\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ - Nano topological space. In section 2, we present a new method to construct $\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ - Nano topological space. In section 3, we introduce new types of open sets $\mathfrak{N}_{\alpha}\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$, $\mathfrak{N}_{\mathcal{S}}\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$, $\mathfrak{N}_{\rho}\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$, $\mathfrak{N}_{\gamma}\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ and $\mathfrak{N}_{\beta}\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ -open sets, and investigate their properties. Further, we describe and characterize new classes of normal spaces namely $\mathfrak{N}\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}\mathfrak{Nl}$ and $\mathfrak{N}_{\mathcal{S}}$ $\mathfrak{D}_{\mathcal{L}}\mathfrak{Nl}$ -spaces.

2 Methodology

2.1 $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ Nano topology

Definition 2.1. Let \mathfrak{K} be an ideal in the universal set U and $M \subseteq U$. Then the Nano left dynamic lower, upper and boundary regions are defined as,

$$\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}(M) = \{\eta \in U : \mathfrak{R}'_1(\eta) \cap M^c \in \mathfrak{K} \text{ and } \mathfrak{R}'_1(\eta) \subseteq M\},$$

$\overline{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}}(M) = \{\eta \in U : \mathfrak{R}'_1(\eta) \cap M \notin \mathfrak{K} \text{ and } \mathfrak{R}'_1(\eta) \cap M \neq \emptyset\}$ where $\mathfrak{R}'_i(\eta) = \{\beta \in U : \mathfrak{R}_i(\eta) \subseteq \mathfrak{R}_i(\beta)\}$ and $\mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}}(M) = \overline{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}}(M) - \mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}(M)R'_i(\eta) = (\beta \in U : R_i(\eta) \subseteq R_i(\beta))$. Then, the Nano left dynamic topology (called $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ - Nano topology) on U with respect $M \subseteq U$ is defined as, $\mathfrak{ND}_{\mathcal{L}}(M) = \{\emptyset, \emptyset, \overline{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}}(M), \mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}(M), \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}}(M)\}$. The collection $\mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}}(M) = \{U, \mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}(M), \mathfrak{B}_{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}}(M)\}$ forms a basis for $\mathfrak{ND}_{\mathcal{L}}(M)$ and the $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ - Nano topological space is denoted by $(U, \mathfrak{ND}_{\mathcal{L}}(M), \mathfrak{K})$. The elements of $\mathfrak{ND}_{\mathcal{L}}(M)$ are called $\mathfrak{ND}_{\mathcal{L}}$ - open sets and its complements are called $\mathfrak{ND}_{\mathcal{L}}$ - closed sets. Then, $\text{int}_{\mathfrak{ND}_{\mathcal{L}}}(M) = \cup_{P \in \mathfrak{ND}_{\mathcal{L}}(M)} \{P/P \subseteq M\}$ and $\text{cl}_{\mathfrak{ND}_{\mathcal{L}}}(M) = \cap_{P \in \mathfrak{ND}_{\mathcal{L}}(M)} \{P/P \supseteq M\}$

Example 2.2 . Let $\mathfrak{K} = \{(\eta, \gamma, \rho, \omega, \tau)\}$, $M = \{\eta, \gamma\}$, $K = \{(\eta, \gamma), (\xi), (\eta, \omega)\}$ and the relation be $Y = \{(\eta, \eta), (\eta, \gamma), (\eta, \rho), (\gamma, \gamma), (\rho, \eta), (v, \omega), (\omega, \tau), (\tau, \gamma)\}$. Then, the corresponding $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ - Nano topology is $ND_{\mathcal{L}}(M) = \{U, \emptyset, (\eta, \gamma), (\eta, \gamma, \rho), (v)\}$.

Definition 2.3. Let $(U, \mathfrak{ND}_{\mathcal{L}}(\mathcal{F}), \mathfrak{K})$ be a $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}$ - Nano topological space. An operator $\eta^{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}} : \wp(U) \rightarrow \wp(U)$ is known as the dynamic function of \mathfrak{K} on U and defined as

$\mathfrak{G}^{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}} = \{\eta \in U : \mathcal{G} \cap \mathfrak{K} \notin \mathfrak{K} \text{ for all } \mathcal{G} \in \mathfrak{ND}_{\mathcal{L}}(\eta)\}$. The corresponding closure operator of $\mathfrak{h}^{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}}$ is defined as $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}^*(\mathfrak{h}) = \mathfrak{h} \cup \mathfrak{h}^{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}}$.

Theorem 2.4. Let K_{α} and K_{β} be the two ideals on the universal set U and $T_{\alpha}, T_{\beta}, H, D \subseteq U$. Then,

1. $\emptyset^{D_{\mathcal{L}}} = \emptyset$
2. If $T_{\alpha} \subset T_{\beta}$ then $T_{\alpha}^{D_{\mathcal{L}}} \subset T_{\beta}^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}$.
3. For any two ideals $K_{\alpha} \supseteq K_{\beta}$ on U , $H^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}(K_{\alpha}) \supseteq H^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}(K_{\beta})$.
4. $H^{D_{\mathcal{L}}} \subset D_{\mathcal{L}}^*(H)$.
5. $(H^{D_{\mathcal{L}}})^{D_{\mathcal{L}}} \subset H^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}$.
6. $H^{D_{\mathcal{L}}} \cup D^{D_{\mathcal{L}}} = (H \cup D)^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}$.
7. $(H \cap D)^{D_{\mathcal{L}}} = H^{D_{\mathcal{L}}} \cap D^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}$.
8. If $H \subset H^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}$ then $H^{D_{\mathcal{L}}} = D_{\mathcal{L}}^*(H)$.

Proof. (1) Proof is trivial. (2) Let $T_{\alpha} \subset T_{\beta}$ and $\eta \in T_{\alpha}^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}$. Suppose $\eta \notin T_{\beta}^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}$. Here $G \cap T_{\alpha} \subseteq G \cap T_{\beta}$ and $G \cap T_{\beta} \in K$ for all $G \in ND_{\mathcal{L}}(\eta)$, we have $G \cap T_{\alpha} \in K$. Therefore $\eta \notin T_{\alpha}^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}$ which is a contradiction. Hence, $T_{\alpha}^{D_{\mathcal{L}}} \subset T_{\beta}^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}$. (3) Let $K_{\beta} \subseteq K_{\alpha}$ and $\eta \in H^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}(K_{\alpha})$. Then $S \cap H \notin K_{\alpha}$ for all $S \in ND_{\mathcal{L}}(\eta)$. Since $S \cap H \notin K_{\beta}$, $\eta \in H^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}(K_{\beta})$. Hence, $H^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}(K_{\alpha}) \supseteq H^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}(K_{\beta})$.

(4) Let $\eta \in H^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}$. Then for all $Z \in ND_{\mathcal{L}}(\eta)$, $Z \cap H \notin K$ which results $Z \cap H = \emptyset$. Hence, $\eta \in D_{\mathcal{L}}^*(H)$ and $H^{D_{\mathcal{L}}} \subset D_{\mathcal{L}}^*(H)$. (5) Proof is trivial from the definition of $H^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}$.

(6) Here, $H \subset H \cup D$ and $D \subset H \cup D$. Then $H^{D_{\mathcal{L}}} \cup D^{D_{\mathcal{L}}} \subseteq (H \cup D)^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}$.

Let $\eta \in (H \cup D)^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}$. Then for all $S \in ND_{\mathcal{L}}(\eta)$, $S \cap (H \cup D) \notin K$ which implies $(S \cap H) \cup (S \cap D) \notin K$. Hence, $S \cap H$ or $S \cap D \notin K$ results that $\eta \in H^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}$ or $\eta \in D^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}$.

Therefore, $\eta \in H^{D_{\mathcal{L}}} \cup D^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}$.

(7) Here, $H \cap D \subset Q$ and $H \cap D \subset D$. Then, $(H \cap D)^{D_{\mathcal{L}}} \subseteq H^{D_{\mathcal{L}}} \cap D^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}$. Conversely, let $\eta \in Q^{D_{\mathcal{L}}} \cap F^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}$. Then for all $Z \in ND_{\mathcal{L}}(\eta)$, $S \cap Q$, $S \cap D \notin K$ results that $S \cap (H \cap D) \notin K$. Therefore, $\eta \in (H \cap D)^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}$.

(8) For all $\mathfrak{G} \subseteq U$, $\mathfrak{h} \subseteq \mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}^*(\mathfrak{h})$. Also, $\mathfrak{G} \subseteq \mathfrak{G}^{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}}$ results that $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}^*(\mathfrak{h}) \subseteq \mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}^*(\mathfrak{G}^{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}})$. Hence, $\mathfrak{h}^{\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}} = \mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{L}}^*(\mathfrak{h})$.

Theorem 2.5. Let $(U, ND_{\mathcal{L}}(F), K)$ be a $D_{\mathcal{L}}$ - Nano topological space with $H, D \subseteq U$. Then,

1. $H \subseteq D_{\mathcal{L}}^*(H)$.
2. $D_{\mathcal{L}}^*(\emptyset) = \emptyset, D_{\mathcal{L}}^*(U) = U$.
3. If $H \subseteq D$ then $D_{\mathcal{L}}^*(H) \subseteq D_{\mathcal{L}}^*(D)$.
4. $D_{\mathcal{L}}^*(H) \cup D_{\mathcal{L}}^*(D) = D_{\mathcal{L}}^*(H \cup D)$.
5. $D_{\mathcal{L}}^*(D_{\mathcal{L}}^*(H)) = D_{\mathcal{L}}^*(H)$.
6. $D_{\mathcal{L}}^*(H \cap D) \subseteq D_{\mathcal{L}}^*(H) \cap D_{\mathcal{L}}^*(D)$.
7. If S is $ND_{\mathcal{L}}$ - open then $S \cap D_{\mathcal{L}}^*(H) \subseteq D_{\mathcal{L}}^*(S \cap H)$.

Proof. (1) Here $H \subseteq H \cup Q^{D_{\mathcal{L}}} = D_{\mathcal{L}}^*(H)$. (2) $D_{\mathcal{L}}^*(\emptyset) = \emptyset \cup \emptyset^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}$ and $D_{\mathcal{L}}^*(U) = U \cup U^{D_{\mathcal{L}}}$.

(3) If $H \subseteq F$ then $H^{D_L} \subseteq F^{D_L}$. Also $H \cup H^{D_L} \subseteq D \cup D^{D_L}$. Hence, $D_L^*(H) \subseteq D_L^*(D)$.

(4) Here, $D_L^*(H \cup D) = (H \cup D) \cup (H \cup D)^{D_L} = (H \cup H^{D_L}) \cup (D \cup D^{D_L}) = D_L^*(H) \cup D_L^*(D)$. (5) Consider $D_L^*(D_L^*(H)) = D_L^*(H \cup H^{D_L}) = D_L^*(H)$. (6) Let $\eta \in D_L^*(H \cap D)$. Since $H \cap D \subseteq H$ and $H \cap D \subseteq D$, $(H \cap D)^{D_L} \subseteq D^{D_L}$ and $(H \cap D)^{D_L} \subseteq D^{D_L}$.

Also, $D_L^*(H \cap D) = (H \cap D) \cup (H \cap D)^{D_L} \subseteq H \cup H^{D_L} = D_L^*(H)$.

Similarly, $D_L^*(H \cap D) \subseteq D_L^*(D)$. Since $\eta \in D_L^*(H \cap D)$, $\eta \in D_L^*(H)$

and $\eta \in D_L^*(D)$. Therefore $\eta \in D_L^*(H) \cap D_L^*(D)$. (7) Let S be a ND_L -open. Then $S \cup (H \cup H^{D_L}) = (S \cap H) \cup (S \cap H^{D_L}) \cup (S \cap H)^{D_L}$. Hence, $S \cap D_L^*(H) \subseteq D_L^*(S \cap H)$.

Remark 2.6. Let $= (\eta, \gamma, \varrho, \omega, \tau)$, $H = \{\eta, \gamma\}$, the relation $D = \{(\eta, \eta), (\eta, \gamma), (\eta, \varrho), (\gamma, \gamma), (\varrho, \eta), (\varrho, \omega), (\omega, \tau), (\tau, \gamma)\}$ and $K_\alpha = \{\emptyset, \{\eta\}, \{\varrho\}, \{\omega\}, \{\eta, \omega\}, \{\eta, \varrho\}, \{\eta, \varrho, \omega\}, \{\varrho, \omega\}\}$, $K_\beta = \{\emptyset, \{\eta\}, \{\omega\}, \{\eta, \omega\}\}$. Then, the following facts have been observed.

i) If $T_\alpha = \{\gamma\}$ and $T_\beta = \{\eta, \gamma, \varrho, \tau\}$ then $T_\beta^{D_L} \supseteq T_\alpha^{D_L}$

ii) $\{\varrho\}^{D_L}(K_\beta) \supseteq \{\varrho\}^{D_L}(K_\alpha)$.

iii) $\{\eta\} \subseteq \{\eta, \tau\}$ but $D_L^*(\eta, \tau) \supseteq D_L^*(\eta)$.

iv) $D_L^*(\{\eta, \gamma\}) \cap D_L^*(\{\eta\}) \supseteq D_L^*(\{\eta, \gamma\} \cap \{\eta\})$.

v) If $S = \{\eta, \gamma, \varrho\}$ and $H = \{\eta, \gamma\}$ then $D_L^*(S \cap H) \supseteq S \cap D_L^*(H)$.

3 Results and Discussion

Definition 3.1. A subset Q of $(U, ND_L(G), K)$ is

a) $N_r D_L$ -open if $Q = \text{int}_{ND_L}(cl_{ND_L}(Q))$.

b) $N_\alpha D_L$ -open if $Q \subseteq \text{int}_{ND_L}(cl_{ND_L}(\text{int}_{ND_L}(Q)))$.

c) $N_s D_L$ -open if $Q \subseteq cl_{ND_L}(\text{int}_{ND_L}(Q))$.

d) $N_p D_L$ -open if $Q \subseteq \text{int}_{ND_L}(cl_{ND_L}(Q))$.

e) $N_\gamma D_L$ -open if $Q \subseteq cl_{ND_L}(\text{int}_{ND_L}(Q)) \cup \text{int}_{ND_L}(cl_{ND_L}(Q))$.

f) $N_\beta D_L$ -open if $Q \subseteq cl_{ND_L}(\text{int}_{ND_L}(cl_{ND_L}(Q)))$.

Theorem 3.2.

a) Every ND_L -open set is $N_\alpha D_L$ -open.

b) Every $N_\alpha D_L$ -open set is $N_p D_L$ -open.

c) Every $N_p D_L$ -open set is $N_\gamma D_L$ -open.

d) Every $N_\beta D_L$ -open set is $N_\gamma D_L$ -open.

e) Every $N_s D_L$ -open set is $N_\gamma D_L$ -open.

Proof. (a) Let Z be a ND_L -open set. Then, $Z = \text{int}_{ND_L}(Z)$ and $cl_{ND_L}(Z) = cl_{ND_L}(\text{int}_{ND_L}(Z))$. Also, $Z \subseteq cl_{ND_L}(Z) = cl_{ND_L}(\text{int}_{ND_L}(Z))$ and $\text{int}_{ND_L}(Z) \subseteq \text{int}_{ND_L}(cl_{ND_L}(\text{int}_{ND_L}(Z)))$. Hence, Z is $N_\alpha D_L$ -open. (b) Let F be $N_\alpha D_L$ -open set. Then $F \subseteq \text{int}_{ND_L}(cl_{ND_L}(\text{int}_{ND_L}(F)))$.

Since $\text{int}_{ND_L}(F) \subseteq F$, $cl_{ND_L}(\text{int}_{ND_L}(F)) \subseteq cl_{ND_L}(F)$.

Also, $\text{int}_{ND_L}(cl_{ND_L}(\text{int}_{ND_L}(F))) \subseteq \text{int}_{ND_L}(cl_{ND_L}(F))$.

This implies that $F \subseteq (\text{int}_{ND_L}(cl_{ND_L}(F)))$. Hence, F is $N_p D_L$ -open. (c) Let L be a $N_p D_L$ -open set. So, $L \subseteq (\text{int}_{ND_L}(cl_{ND_L}(F)))$. Also, $L \subseteq (\text{int}_{ND_L}(cl_{ND_L}(F)) \cup cl_{ND_L}(\text{int}_{ND_L}(F)))$.

Hence, L is $N_\gamma D_L$ -open. (d) Let O be $N_\beta D_L$ -open set.

Then, $O \subseteq cl_{ND_L}(\text{int}_{ND_L}(cl_{ND_L}(Q)))$. Also, $O \subseteq (\text{int}_{ND_L}(cl_{ND_L}(Q)))$.

Therefore, $O \subseteq \text{int}_{ND_L}(cl_{ND_L}(\text{int}_{ND_L}(F)))$. Hence, O is $N_\gamma D_L$ -open. (e) Let M be a $N_s D_L$ -open set. Then

$M \subseteq cl_{ND_L}(\text{int}_{ND_L}(M))$.

Also, $M \subseteq cl_{ND_L}(\text{int}_{ND_L}(M)) \cup \text{int}_{ND_L}(cl_{ND_L}(M))$. Hence, M is $N_\gamma D_L$ -open.

Remark 3.3. From the example 2.2, we have the following facts.

i) $\{\eta\}$ is $N_\alpha D_L$ -open but not ND_L -open.

ii) $\{\gamma, \varrho\}$ is $N_p D_L$ -open but not $N_\alpha D_L$ -open.

- iii) (η, γ, ω) is $N_\gamma D_L$ -open but not $N_p D_L$ -open.
- iv) $\{\eta, \varrho, \tau\}$ is $N_\gamma D_L$ -open but not $N_\beta D_L$ -open.
- v) $(\gamma, \varrho, \omega)$ is $N_\gamma D_L$ -open but not $N_s D_L$ -open.

Definition 3.4. Let Q be a subset of $(U, ND_L(G), K)$. Then,

1. Q is D_L^* -closed if $D_L^*(Q) = Q$ whenever $Q \subseteq S$, S is ND_L -open.
2. Q is $N_{S L}^- D_L$ -closed if $D_L^*(Q) \subseteq S$ whenever $Q \subseteq S$, S is ND_L -open. The collection of all $N_{S L}^- D_L$ -closed sets are denoted by $D_L^* C(G)$.
3. Q is $N_{S L}^- D_L$ -closed if $D_L^*(Q) \subseteq S$ whenever $Q \subseteq S$, S is $N_s D_L$ -open. The collection of all $N_{S L}^- D_L$ -closed sets are denoted by $N_{S L}^- D_L C(G)$.

Definition 3.5. Let $\Lambda : (U_a, N^a, K_a) \rightarrow (U_b, N^b, K_b)$ be a map. Then,

1. Λ is $N_{S L}^- D_L$ -continuous function if $\Lambda^{-1}(Q)$ is $N_{S L}^- D_L$ -open subset of (U_a, N^a, K_a) whenever Q is ND_L -open subset of (U_b, N^b, K_b) .
2. Λ is $N_{S L}^- D_L$ -irresolute if $\Lambda^{-1}(Q)$ is $N_{S L}^- D_L$ -open whenever Q is $N_{S L}^- D_L$ -open.

Example 3.6. Let $U = (\eta, \gamma, \varrho, \omega, \tau)$, $S = \{\eta, \gamma\}$, $K = \{\emptyset, (\eta), (\omega), (\eta, \omega)\}$ and the relation be $Y = \{(\eta, \eta), (\eta, \gamma), (\eta, \varrho), (\gamma, \gamma), (\varrho, \eta), (\varrho, \xi), (\xi, \tau), (\tau, \gamma)\}$. Then $ND_L(G) = \{U, \emptyset, (\eta, \gamma), (\eta, \gamma, \varrho), (\varrho)\}$.

$D_L^* C(S) = \{U, \emptyset, (\eta), (\omega), (\xi, \tau), (\eta, \omega, \tau), (\varrho, \omega, \tau), (\eta, \gamma, \omega, \tau), \{\eta, \varrho, \omega, \tau\}$ and,

$N_{S L}^- D_L C(S) = \{U, \emptyset, (\eta), (\gamma), (\omega), (\eta, \omega), (\eta, \tau), (\gamma, \omega), (\gamma, \tau), (\omega, \tau), (\eta, \omega, \tau), (\varrho, \xi, \tau), (\eta, \gamma, \omega, \tau), (\eta, v, \omega, \tau), \{\gamma, \varrho, \omega, \tau\}$. Also,

the mapping $\Lambda_\alpha : U \rightarrow U$ as defined by $\Lambda_\alpha(\eta) = (\eta, \gamma)$,

$\Lambda_\alpha(\gamma) = (\eta, \gamma, \varrho)$, $\Lambda_\alpha(\varrho) = (\varrho)$, $\Lambda_\alpha(\omega) = (\omega)$, $\Lambda_\alpha(\tau) = (\tau)$, is both $N_{S L}^- D_L$ -continuous and

$N_{S L}^- D_L$ -irresolute.

3.1. $N_{S L}^- D_L$ Nl-spaces

Definition 3.7. Let $(U, ND_L(G), K)$ be a dynamic Nano topological space. Then,

1. U is ND_L -Normal space (known as ND_L Nl-space) if for any pair of non-empty disjoint ND_L -closed sets W_η and W_ψ of $(U, ND_L(G), K)$, there exist ND_L -open sets Y_η and Y_ψ of $(U, ND_L(G), K)$ with $W_\eta \subset Y_\eta$ and $W_\psi \subset Y_\psi$.
2. U is $N_{S L}^- D_L$ -Normal space (known as $N_{S L}^- D_L$ Nl-space) if for any pair of non-empty disjoint ND_L -closed sets W_η and W_ψ of $(U, ND_L(G), K)$, there exist $N_{S L}^- D_L$ -open sets Y_η and Y_ψ of $(U, ND_L(G), K)$ with $W_\eta \subset Y_\eta$ and $W_\psi \subset Y_\psi$.

Theorem 3.8. Every ND_L Nl-space is $N_{S L}^- D_L$ Nl-space.

Proof. Let $(U, ND_L(G), K)$ be a ND_L Nl-space and W_η and W_ψ be two disjoint non-empty ND_L -closed sets. Then there exists a disjoint non-empty pair of ND_L -open sets Y_η and Y_ψ of $(U, ND_L(G), K)$ with $W_\eta \subset Y_\eta$ and $W_\psi \subset Y_\psi$. Also, every ND_L -open sets are $N_{S L}^- D_L$ -open sets. Then, Y_η and Y_ψ are $N_{S L}^- D_L$ -open sets. So, $(U, ND_L(G), K)$ is $N_{S L}^- D_L$ Nl-space.

Remark 3.9. From the example 2.2, $\{\rho, v, \tau\}$ is $N_{S L}^- D_L$ -open but not ND_L -open. Therefore every $N_{S L}^- D_L$ Nl-space need not be a ND_L Nl-space.

Theorem 3.10. If $(U, ND_L(G), K)$ is $N_{S L}^- D_L$ Nl-space then for every pair of ND_L -open sets

W_η and W_ψ with $W_\eta \cap W_\psi = U$, there exist $N_{S L}^- D_L$ -closed sets Y_η and Y_ψ

with $Y_\eta \subset W_\eta$ and $Y_\psi \subset W_\psi$ and $Y_\eta \cap Y_\psi = U$.

Proof. Let W_η and W_ψ be ND_L -open sets in $(U, ND_L(G), K)$ with $W_\eta \cap W_\psi = U$. Then W_η^c and W_ψ^c are disjoint ND_L -closed sets. Since $(U, ND_L(G), K)$ is $N_{S L}^- D_L$ Nl-space,

there exists a pair of $N_{S L}^- D_L$ -open sets L_η and L_ψ such that $W_\eta^c \subset L_\eta$ and $W_\psi^c \subset L_\psi$.

This implies that $Y_\eta = W_\eta^c$ and $Y_\psi = W_\psi^c$ are $N_{S L}^- D_L$ -closed sets such that $Y_\eta \subset W_\eta$

and $Y_\psi \subset W_\psi$ with $Y_\eta \cap Y_\psi = U$.

Theorem 3.11. Let $\Lambda : (U_a, N^a, K_a) \rightarrow (U_b, N^b, K_b)$ be a ND_L -continuous bijective function and $N_{S L}^- D_L$ -open function. If U_a is a ND_L Nl-space, then U_b is a $N_{S L}^- D_L$ Nl-space.

Proof. Let W_η and W_ψ be two disjoint ND_L -closed sets in (U_b, N^b, K_b) .

Since Λ is ND_L -continuous bijective, $\Lambda^{-1}(W_\eta)$ and $\Lambda^{-1}(W_\psi)$ are disjoint ND_L -closed sets

in (U_a, N^a, K_a) . Also since U_a is ND_L -space, there exists a disjoint ND_L -open sets Y_η and Y_ψ with $\Lambda^{-1}(W_\eta) \subset Y_\eta$ and $\Lambda^{-1}(W_\psi) \subset Y_\psi$. Then, $W_\eta \subset \Lambda(Y_\eta)$ and $W_\psi \subset \Lambda(Y_\psi)$.

Also, $\Lambda(Y_\eta)$ and $\Lambda(Y_\psi)$ are ND_L -open sets in (U_b, N^b, K_b) .

Since Λ is bijective, $\Lambda(Y_\eta) \cap \Lambda(Y_\psi) = \emptyset$. Hence, (U_b, N^b, K_b) is $N_{S^L}^-D$ -space.

Theorem 3.12. Let $\Lambda : (U_a, N^a, K_a) \rightarrow (U_b, N^b, K_b)$ be $N_{S^L}^-D$ -continuous and ND_L -closed bijection and U_b be a ND_L -space. Then U_a is a $N_{S^L}^-D$ -space.

Proof:

Let W_η and W_ψ be two disjoint ND_L -closed sets in (U_b, N^b, K_b) . Then $\Lambda(W_\eta)$ and $\Lambda(W_\psi)$ are disjoint closed sets in (U_b, N^b, K_b) . Since U_b is ND_L -space, there exist disjoint ND_L -open sets Y_η and Y_ψ with $\Lambda(W_\eta) \subset Y_\eta$ and $\Lambda(W_\psi) \subset Y_\psi$. Therefore $W_\eta \subset \Lambda^{-1}(Y_\eta)$ and $W_\psi \subset \Lambda^{-1}(Y_\psi)$. Since f is $N_{S^L}^-D$ -continuous, $\Lambda^{-1}(Y_\eta)$ and $\Lambda^{-1}(Y_\psi)$

are $N_{S^L}^-D$ -open sets in (U_a, N^a, K_a) . Also, $\Lambda^{-1}(Y_\eta) \cap \Lambda^{-1}(Y_\psi) = \emptyset$.

Hence (U_a, N^a, K_a) is $N_{S^L}^-D$ -space.

Theorem 3.13. If $\Lambda : (U_a, N^a, K_a) \rightarrow (U_b, N^b, K_b)$ is $N_{S^L}^-D$ -irresolute, ND_L -closed bijection and U_b is $N_{S^L}^-D$ -space, then U_a is a $N_{S^L}^-D$ -space.

Proof. Let W_η and W_ψ be two disjoint ND_L -closed sets in (U_b, N^b, K_b) .

Here Λ is ND_L -closed bijection, $\Lambda(W_\eta)$ and $\Lambda(W_\psi)$ are disjoint ND_L -closed sets in (U_b, N^b, K_b) . Since (U_b, N^b, K_b) is $N_{S^L}^-D$ -space, there exist disjoint $N_{S^L}^-D$ -open sets in Y_η and Y_ψ such that $\Lambda(W_\eta) \subset Y_\eta$ and $\Lambda(W_\psi) \subset Y_\psi$. Since Λ is $N_{S^L}^-D$ -irresolute,

$\Lambda^{-1}(Y_\eta)$ and $\Lambda^{-1}(Y_\psi)$ are $N_{S^L}^-D$ -open sets in (U_a, N^a, K_a) . Also $\Lambda^{-1}(Y_\eta) \cap \Lambda^{-1}(Y_\psi) = \emptyset$.

Hence, (U_a, N^a, K_a) is $N_{S^L}^-D$ -space.

3.2. $N_{QS^L}^-D$ -spaces

Definition 3.14. A subset Q_ζ of $(U, ND_L(G), K)$ is a $N_{\pi^L}^-D$ -open set if it is the finite union of $N_{\pi^L}^-D$ -opensets.

Definition 3.15. A D_L -nano topological space $(U, ND_L(G), K)$ is $N_{QS^L}^-D$ -space if for any pair of disjoint $N_{\pi^L}^-D$ -closed sub sets W_η, W_ψ of U , there exist disjoint $N_{S^L}^-D$ -open sets Y_η, Y_ψ such that $W_\eta \subseteq Y_\eta$ and $W_\psi \subseteq Y_\psi$.

Theorem 3.16. If $(U, ND_L(G), K)$ is a D_L -nano topological space, then the following are equivalent.

a) U is $N_{QS^L}^-D$ -space.

b) For any pair of $N_{\pi^L}^-D$ -open sets W_η and W_ψ of U with $W_\eta \cup W_\psi = U$, there are $N_{S^L}^-D$ -closed subsets Y_η, Y_ψ of U such that $Y_\eta \subseteq W_\eta$ and $Y_\psi \subseteq W_\psi$ with $Y_\eta \cup Y_\psi = U$.

c) For every $N_{\pi^L}^-D$ -closed set W_η and every $N_{\pi^L}^-D$ -open set Y_η with $W_\eta \subseteq Y_\eta$, there is C_η with $W_\eta \subseteq C_\eta \subseteq N_{S^L}^-D$ - $C(C_\eta) \subseteq Y_\eta$.

d) For any pair of disjoint $N_{\pi^L}^-D$ -closed subsets W_η and W_ψ of U , there exist $N_{S^L}^-D$ -open subsets C_η and C_ψ of U with $W_\eta \subseteq C_\eta, W_\psi \subseteq C_\psi$ and $N_{S^L}^-D$ - $C(C_\eta) \cap N_{S^L}^-D$ - $C(C_\psi) = \emptyset$.

Proof . Assume (a).

Let W_η and W_ψ be $N_{\pi^L}^-D$ -open subsets of $N_{QS^L}^-D$ -space U with $W_\eta \cup W_\psi = U$. Then W_η^c and W_ψ^c are the $N_{\pi^L}^-D$ -closed subsets of U . Also, there exist disjoint $N_{S^L}^-D$ -open subsets L_η, L_ψ of U with $W_\eta^c \subseteq L_\eta$ and $W_\psi^c \subseteq L_\psi$. Let $Y_\eta = L_\eta^c$ and $Y_\psi = L_\psi^c$. Then L_η and L_ψ are $N_{S^L}^-D$ -closed subsets of U with $L_\eta \subseteq W_\eta$ and $L_\psi \subseteq W_\psi$. Hence (b) is proved.

Assume (b). Let W_η be any $N_{\pi}^{-D}_L$ -closed set and C_η be any $N_{\pi}^{-D}_L$ -open subset of U with $W_\eta \subseteq Y_\eta$. Then W_η^c and C_η are $N_{\pi}^{-D}_L$ -open subsets of U with $W_\eta^c \cup Y_\eta = U$. Then there exist $N_{S}^{-D}_L$ -closed subsets of UL_η, L_ψ of U with $L_\eta \subseteq W_\eta^c$ and $L_\psi \subseteq Y_\eta$ and $L_\eta \cup L_\psi = U$. Also, $W_\eta \subseteq L_\eta^c, Y_\eta^c \subseteq L_\psi^c$ and $L_\eta^c \cap L_\psi^c = \emptyset$. Let $C_\eta = L_\eta^c$ and $C_\psi = L_\psi^c$. Then C_η and C_ψ are disjoint $N_{S}^{-D}_L$ -open sets with $W_\eta \subseteq L_\eta$ and $Y_\eta^c \subseteq C_\psi$ which gives $C_\psi^c \subseteq Y_\eta$. Since C_ψ^c is $N_{S}^{-D}_L$ -closed, $N_{S}^{-D}_L C(C_\eta) \subseteq Y_\eta$.

Hence (c) is proved.

Assume (c). Let W_η and W_ψ be any pair of disjoint $N_{\pi}^{-D}_L$ -closed sets of U .

Then $W_\eta \subseteq W_\psi^c$ and W_ψ^c is $N_{\pi}^{-D}_L$ -open. After that, there is a $N_{S}^{-D}_L$ -open sets Y_η of U with $W_\eta \subseteq Y_\eta \subseteq N_{S}^{-D}_L C(Y_\eta) \subseteq W_\psi^c$. Also $W_\eta \subseteq Y_\eta$, and $W_\psi \subseteq (N_{S}^{-D}_L C(Y_\eta))^c$.

Let $Y_\psi = (N_{S}^{-D}_L C(Y_\eta))^c$. Then Y_ψ is $N_{S}^{-D}_L$ -open subset of U .

Therefore, $W_\eta \subseteq Y_\eta$ and $W_\psi \subseteq Y_\psi$ with $N_{S}^{-D}_L C(Y_\eta) \cap N_{S}^{-D}_L C(Y_\psi) = \emptyset$.

Hence (d) is proved. From the definition of $N_{QS}^{-D}_L$ Nl -space, (d) \Rightarrow (a) can be easily verified.

Theorem 3.17. If $\Lambda : (U_a, N^a, K_a) \rightarrow (U_b, N^b, K_b)$ is ND_L -open and ND_L -continuous bijective function and (U_a, N^a, K_a) is $N_{QS}^{-D}_L$ Nl -space, then $\Lambda(U_a)$ is $N_{QS}^{-D}_L$ Nl -space.

Proof. Let L_η and L_ψ be two disjoint $N_{\pi}^{-D}_L$ -closed subsets of $\Lambda(U_a)$. Then, $\Lambda^{-1}(L_\eta)$ and $\Lambda^{-1}(L_\psi)$ are disjoint $N_{\pi}^{-D}_L$ -closed subsets of U_a . Since U_a is a $N_{QS}^{-D}_L$ Nl -space, there exist

$N_{S}^{-D}_L$ -open subsets Y_η and Y_ψ of U_a with $\Lambda^{-1}(L_\eta) \subseteq Y_\eta, \Lambda^{-1}(L_\psi) \subseteq Y_\psi$ and

$\Lambda(L_\eta) \cap \Lambda(L_\psi) = \emptyset$. So, $\Lambda(L_\eta)$ and $\Lambda(L_\psi)$ are disjoint $N_{S}^{-D}_L$ -open sub sets of $\Lambda(U_a)$. Hence, $\Lambda(U_a)$ is $N_{QS}^{-D}_L$ Nl -space.

4 Conclusion

The present work explores the concept of D_L -Nano topological space and analyses two distinct normal spaces $ND_L Nl$ and $N_{QS}^{-D}_L$ Nl -spaces in the D_L -Nano topological space. Our research results contribute to the stream of investigations concerning several kinds of descriptions of D_L -Nano topological spaces. Future studies can characterize the structure of regular spaces and investigate the real - life applications of D_L -Nano topological spaces.

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